

Managing Stakeholder Conduct, Social Responsibility, and Ethical Climate: The Case of Curaçao

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Article History

Received: 20.06.2024

Accepted: 01.07.2024

Published: 19.07.2024

Abstract: The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of social responsibility practices and ethical climates conveyed by representatives of commercial and non-commercial business units within the country of Curaçao. The questionnaire was administered to 183 business clients to examine impacts upon the attainment of unit financial goals and on the development of strategic alliances relating to tourism perpetuation and sustainment. Findings indicated differences in social responsibility and ethical climates by business units and relative to the type of goal attainment considered. Implications would be for the management and business representatives to incorporate and highlight the importance of the identified social responsibility and ethical climates during negotiations with their tourism clients, thus increasing the likelihood of sustaining tourism in Curaçao.

Keywords: Curacao, Ethical Climate, Social Responsibility, Strategic Goal Attainment, Sustainable Tourism.

Cite this article:

Fjelstul, J., Johnson, C., Lasten, E., Upchurch, R. S., (2024). Managing Stakeholder Conduct, Social Responsibility, and Ethical Climate: The Case of Curaçao. *ISAR Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 2(7), 66-81.

Introduction

In many developing countries, business units associated with tourism development generate short-term and long-term market value from contribution of stakeholders and through a combination of established economic, environmental, financial, and social objectives (Brulhart et al., 2019; Hammer & Pivo, 2017; Thijssens et al., 2015). Such objectives are tempered by a business unit's underlying corporate social responsibility (SR) and ethical climate (EC) (Brown & Forster, 2013; Victor & Cullen, 1988). A fundamental principle aligned with sustaining the ebb and flow of transactions between company representatives and their external clients, therefore, hinges upon the representative-to-client co-creation process. From the client's perspective, furthermore, ethical and socially responsible actions performed by a company's representative is seen as an indicator of company integrity relative to service offerings, business practices, and philosophies (Freudenreich et al., 2020; Garriga & Melé, 2004).

Specific to internal integrity, a growing sector of research pertaining to stakeholder theory has shown incorporating and implementing socially responsible practices with ethical practices produces competitive advantages while generating sustained positive trade relations (Waheed & Zhang, 2020; Freudenreich et al., 2020; Freeman et al., 2020; Crane & Ruebottom, 2011;

Freeman et al., 2007; Fisher & Reuber, 2003; Freeman, 1984). The studies, however, were conducted within economic, geographical and mature infrastructures germane to nations with developed economies. For example, Waheed and Zhang (2020) focused on managing the impact of corporate social responsibility and ethical climate practices upon identified business performance metrics. A gap in the literature is that of related studies with similar focus but for developing countries. The current study addressed such gap by exploring respective business practices in the developing country of Curacao, an island with a small scale economy, limited infrastructure resources and capabilities, and geographically located within the Caribbean by focusing on how management could achieve sustainable performance by leveraging social responsibility and ethical climate practices as tactical tools. The casual impact of SR and EC actions taken by internal stakeholders upon specified strategic goal attainment is presently unknown for business units aligned with the developing economy of Curaçao.

Study Premise

Numerous studies have noted implications resulting from co-created transactional patterns between stakeholders filtered through culturally driven SR and EC frameworks (Waheed & Zhang, 2020; Freudenreich et al., 2020; Brulhart et al., 2019; Thijssens et al., 2015; Skudiene & Auruskeviciene, 2012; Baumgartner & Ebner, 2010; Brammer et al., 2007; Upchurch & Ruhland, 1996; Victor &

Cullen, 1988). Within those parameters, the current study adopted Freeman's definition of an internal stakeholder whereby a company representative, and as a result of their employment capacity, influences the achievement of financial objectives particular to performance targets set by he/she/their business units (Freeman, 1984). Such assertion is echoed by Singh (2010) and Tromp (2007), arguing stakeholder engagement specific to island economies are a) an integral part of trade growth, b) such transactions are complex and highly dependent upon individual interactions, beliefs, and preferences of individuals, c) actions taken by company agents are vital to the attainment of regional and global trade, and d) engagement in trade and business transactions are deeply rooted in socially responsible and ethical behaviors as communicated by those representatives. Within the context of the current study, an island economy is defined by the World Customs Organization (2019) as an economy comprised of a) a lack of connectedness with international value chains, b) typified as being geographically removed from large markets thus resulting in elevated transportation costs, c) are limited in maritime and air access, d) have limited production and service capacities, and e) are highly prone to natural disasters. Given those limitations, the existing body of research surrounding a country's trade growth has largely concentrated on the direct and indirect economic impacts of services rendered by a country's private and public business units, likewise consequential to a developing country's status as an economic power. Academic research, however, has unheeded business representative influence upon attaining unit goals, intermediated by social responsibility and ethical business practices relative to the solicitation and sustainment of strategic goals assigned to an island country (Madanaguli, et al, 2022; Pereira & Gadotti dos Anjos, 2021).

The current study, therefore, showcased the Caribbean country of Curacao, in particular with the underlying premise that actions performed by representatives of Curacao's private and public business and government units (i.e., internal stakeholders) may influence achieving stated organizational performance targets. Four commercial and non-commercial business units were explored due to their direct relationship with fostering and sustaining inbound and outbound tourism transactions: a) Curacao's Ministry of Traffic, Transport, and Spatial Planning (TTSP), previously named the Ministry of Traffic, Transport, and Spatial Planning, b) Curacao's Chamber of Commerce and Industry, c) Curacao Bankers Association, and d) the Curacao Trade and Industry Association.

This manuscript has been outlined as follows. First, stakeholder theoretical perspectives, social responsibility, and noted ethical work climate literature were examined and summarized. Next, the article outlines the study's methodology, data collection, and defined the study conditions. The article concludes by depicting the current study's findings, related implications, and offers future research suggestions.

Literature Review

Stakeholder Management, Roles, and Impacts

The theoretical foundation for this study is premised upon the body of knowledge surrounding stakeholder theory, more specifically, the stakeholder's role in forming impressions within a transactional context. At a fundamental level, stakeholder theory portends that an organization's strategic outcomes represent a composite

interplay between intrapersonal, interpersonal, and external social dynamics as interconnected with moral, social, and ethical responsibilities. Therefore, a 'stakeholder' is defined as an individual or individuals who either influence or are influenced by existing practices and philosophies in pursuit of meeting work unit performance targets (Carroll, 2021). Of particular importance, Khairi, Bahri, and Artha (2021) concluded perpetuation of positive business transactions are strongly influenced by political, economic, societal, and management quality. The resulting transactional process has become a point of debate by business strategists respective to how a business creates value in the minds of their intended consumers. Consequently, examinations of stakeholder behaviors and surrounding conditions are of utmost importance to the refinement of existing stakeholder theories (Freeman, et al., 2020; Parmar, et al., 2019). Furthermore, Barney and Harrison (2020) noted underlying business-to-client processes are multidimensional in nature, thus generating a growing body of knowledge in the stakeholder theory space concerning the interactive effects of intermediary factors.

Clients (external stakeholders) vector information in an effort to answer the age-old question of whether agents of a company are 'practicing what they preach', thus in turn, denoting credibility and trustworthiness of a company representative and the company in particular (Donaldson and Preston, 1995). Additionally, stakeholder theory and its associated sub-themes of SR and EC have gained influence in application to international business contexts as a result of societal changes (Kivits & Sawang, 2021; Waheed & Zhang, 2020; Mitchell, et al., 1997). It should also be understood that the stakeholder co-creation transactional process is managerial in nature, meaning collective actions taken by company representatives influence attitudes and guide policies, practices and procedures between company representatives with external constituent stakeholders comprised of associations, communities, political groups, suppliers, investors, etc. as overseen by management (Donaldson & Preston, 1995). Lastly, we concur with Freeman, Phillips and Sisodia (2020) in that stakeholder theory embodies three distinctive foundational elements: a) human representatives are vital to the transactional process by actively engaging in an interactive (co-creation) process with clients, b) those same internal representatives align organizational values, mores, and ethical conduct for the purpose of achieving identified internal and external performance targets, and c) those same representatives display a heightened understanding of their role and their company's role in being socially conscious. It is the latter foundational element which highlights the importance of an evolving body of literature surrounding internal stakeholder's role in interacting with external clients by means of social responsibility and ethical business practices. Relative to Curacao, this is a critical notation within the context that economic responsibility in a developing country is significantly impacted by high unemployment, minimization of direct foreign investments, talent shortages, and high rates of poverty, thus highlighting the importance of the internal stakeholder's influence upon creating a trustworthy relationship between both parties (Carroll, 2021; Visser, 2011). This bilateral process of building mutual trust is fundamental to establishing reciprocal value for both parties (Crane, 2020).

In closing, and as previously alluded, the concept of sustainable trade relations is integrally embedded in the study of

social responsibility and ethical business conduct and therefore has become popular in business and stakeholder literature (Carroll, 2021). The following paragraphs summarize key studies noting the intermediary role that SR and EC practices wield upon in the value creation process.

Social Responsibility Practices

As mentioned previously, the concept of sustainable trade relations is integrally embedded in the study of social responsibility and ethical business conduct and therefore has become quite popular in business and academic literature. Hence, the following expand upon the role of internal stakeholders via the lens of SR and EC activities to business operations either to society or to a company's external stakeholders.

Thijssens et al. (2015) determined that customers of publicly held companies expected company representatives to abide by socially responsible practices of which transactions produce a) positive customer perceptions of a company, b) increases company profits, and c) sustain transactions resulting from the company representative's integrity (Brulhart et al, 2019). In advancing that relationship, Li et al. (2022) discovered that unethical supervisory behaviors led to the perpetuation of unscrupulous behavior by staff, thus challenging the company's overall value proposition. It was this focus upon a company's value proposition that Freudenreich et al. (2020) noted customer perception of a company's value proposition is a manifestation of how clearly a company representative articulates his/her company's social responsibility values. Relative to the service sectors of recreation, travel and tourism, lodging, foodservice, and leisure service, Arian, Sands and Tooley (2023) determined that socially responsible actions as practiced by company service providers led to superior financial performance; however, this same relationship did not hold true for industrial-oriented companies. Brown and Forster (2013) determined that a tradeoff existed between taking actions which were based on socially acceptable rules versus those of engaging in actions which were an act of goodness or kindness (beneficence) and heterogeneity of customer needs (Miles, 2017). Furthermore, cultural differences exist, are pervasive, and must be considered when promoting products and services to external stakeholders (Song & Kang, 2019). This evolving body of knowledge surrounding customer engagement via the lens of social responsibility is succinctly summarized by Savage et al. (2010) whereby customer transactions are a) interdependent, b) value propositions are clearly articulated by both parties, c) grounded in mutual trust, and d) align with prevailing social and ethical responsibilities of the client. Lastly, and very pertinent to the current study, Coles, et al (2013) noted that a pressing need exists to better understand the role of social responsibility as it relates to governance and management of businesses. It is therefore imperative to apply and challenge mainstream philosophies comprising the evolving state of CSR theoretical models.

Ethical Work Climate Practices

Relative to the role of stakeholders within the arena of ethical business practices, Dib-Slammi, Grolleau and Mzoughi (2023) determined that being a representative from a 'foreign' company is culturally based within the context that ethical conduct is grounded in cultural morals as to whether behavior is acceptable or not. Extending that concept, Waheed and Zhang (2020) studied the linkage of social responsibility and ethical practices in terms of

environmental responsibility, community responsibility, customer responsibility, and interaction of government rules and regulations upon sustainable competitive performance for businesses operating in the developed economies of China and Pakistan. In the Waheed and Zang (2020) study, they determined that ethical climate practices mediated corporate social responsibility actions. More importantly, management's oversight of ethical behavior was positively associated with deployment of socially responsible practices which, in turn, influenced financial performance of those businesses. In related studies, Wu et al. (2022) and Burke (2022) noted a positive linkage between trust, company reputation, supplier actions resulting from fraudulent activities as practiced by company representatives. Although not as specific in terms of item measurement, Weeden (2002) noted that service-oriented business providers recognized the importance of leveraging ethical business practices of which internal practices were viewed by clients as offering that company a significant competitive advantage. Power et al (2017) noted ethical business conduct is comprised of personal characteristics of intuitionism, benevolence, a future orientation, and humility, thus noting the power of the individual in the co-creation process (Power, et al. 2017). Skinner (2019) offered that processes associated with maintaining growth in available products and services are influenced by cultural factors as well as tempered by local value systems. On the topic of building rapport, inappropriate conduct attributed to a company representative was associated with a lessened desire by the external stakeholder in continuing further transactions with that specific trade partner (Greenwood & Van Buren III, 2010). Continuing onward with impacts associated with ethical conduct as practiced by company representatives, Russo and Perrini (2010) and Gilbert and Rasche (2008) determined that company goals assigned to small to medium enterprises were positively influenced by the act of complete transparency in business transactions. From a management engagement perspective, Li et al. (2022) discovered that staff members were inclined to cover-up their immediate supervisor's unethical actions even though such behaviors were potentially deleterious to their organization's image. Of particular note, employees high in Machiavellianism mirrored unethical supervisor conduct to an accentuated degree in expectation of reciprocity from his/her supervisor.

Role of place agents upon place attachment and branding management

In agreement with Tottenbord, Ooi, and Hardy (2022), a destination's attraction to society exists via a complex interplay of stakeholder relationships of which images are delivered through actions taken by government bodies, local businesses, companies, international business entities, and investors. The actions taken by a community's stakeholders, or for the purpose of this study those entities represent the *destination or place* of Curaçao, influence perceptions perceived by external businesses and tourists desiring to visit or engage in leisure or business transactions within the country. In short, the practices presented by a country's stakeholders are therefore vital to promoting places and services to inbound societal constituencies. Therefore, a country's brand or attraction is perceived as legitimate when the practices and services offered exist as promised, are authentic, engaging, and present a positive image of the place (Boisen et al., 2011; Kemp et al., 2012; Insch and Walters, 2018).

Furthermore, the normative actions, meanings, symbols, practices, and collaborative processes taken by the various place stakeholders in accordance with the goals assigned to those administrative units will vary by the strategic goals assigned to those units (Hankinson, 2009). In agreement, and according to Gulisova, Horbel and Noe (2023), it is therefore very important for a place to identify internal stakeholders and their roles in shaping the branding process and the behavioral engagement actions employed during transactional processes. Moreover, we, the authors agree that a territory, or in this case an island country, is part of the co-creation process by means of the combined intentions of practices taken by its stakeholders, past, present and future which in turn means that the attractiveness of place is 'characterized by the harmony of the needs and behaviors of its stakeholders (Gulisova, Horbel & Noe, 2023). A primary implication offered by Gulisova, Horbel and Noe's (2023) was that the systematic collection, reflection, and assessment of 'actor' practices is necessary in understanding the collaborative and cumulative effects conveyed to external stakeholders (e.g., inbound business and tourism) seeking engagement in place-oriented products and services as expressed. Such reflections would then be manifested in policies instituted by overarching businesses or government units representing the geographical area of interest. Continuing onward with local official or bureaucrat influence, Doyle (2019) designed a study focusing on the influence of governmental policies upon place branding meaning the tangible (physical features both natural and manmade) and intangible attributes (culture) as to how people perceive or expect to experience a place. The crux of their analysis focused upon collaborative efforts expressed by residents, area businesses and policymakers upon the development and implementation of a place brand...and when done in a collaborative fashion, these local stakeholders generated a sustainable brand. Thus, balancing intended benefits of policy for residents and local businesses and the international image as projected to in-bound businesses and tourists. In support of the influence that place agents have upon place attractiveness and branding, Kallstrom and Siljeklint (2024) noted that agents of place branding must be mindful of paradoxes presented during transactions given their role within the participatory place branding process whereby the addressing of opposing expectations can lead to value discussions and development of place brand. Moreover, the process of professionalizing place development interests is premised upon transnationality of common threads pertaining to living, working, and experiencing of place branding, home and abroad of which attainment of those respective goals must be in alignment, and if not, conflict will ensue concerning development and social sustainability of places (Dupre, 2019). In terms of perpetuating sustainable tourism strategies, Ebrahim and Ganguli (2023) conducted a study focused upon the growing medical tourism segment and summarized that traveler appeal pertaining to medical tourism had negative spillover for community residents resulting from perceived negative impacts as communicated by place leaders, thus showing a strong connection between place practices and impact upon place attractiveness. Breek, Eshuis and Hermes (2022) studied the role of governmental planning officials (local street level bureaucrats), relative to their participatory role in municipality placemaking. They noted the necessity of their collaborative linking pin functions as set within the act of practicing and conveying acceptable rules of conduct with

residents relative to external stakeholders use of community place services, thus leading to positive or negative support by residents. Grocke, Eversole, and Hawkins (2022) studied the role of leadership in maintaining a balance between a community's state of 'being versus becoming' and determined that there were six differing strategies to be deployed as assigned to six unique place attachment processes. Their key message concerned unique leader behaviors and strategies upon proper alignment of place resources and networks allocation when properly aligned and deployed would improve or protect the values of the place. Lastly, Baccarani, Cassani, Rossato, and Cavallo (2019) noted that all actors whether business, individual customers, or households experience co-created value resulting in usage of place resources. Tourism-oriented firms, therefore, while conducting transactions develop place awareness when it realizes that it is not a guest of the territory but acts as an agent of the 'territory' for short term output and long-term processes.

In summary, there are two overarching important points concerning the role place agents influence upon place tourism and sustainability; the first being that place agents are vital in communicating, promoting and sustaining place development which align with values of local residents; and second, those same place agents, by means of their professional demeanor and assigned communication and placement strategies create positive place attachment images to inbound businesses as well as travelers who are seeking a mutually acceptable place experience.

Impact of CSR and ethical conduct influences upon sustainable tourism

In alignment and context of promoting Curaçao as a preferred destination, the authors incorporated the perceived impact of corporate social responsibility practices and ethical conduct as practiced by Curaçao place agents, meaning tourism-oriented businesses and government officials upon businesses and individuals seeking place experiences within the country of Curaçao. The following section contains studies pertaining to the importance and impact of CSR and ethical conduct upon place attractiveness and brand awareness.

Corporate social responsibility as set within the context of the enclosed study is defined as fulfilling touted social responsibilities, giving back to the community, acting in the best interest of society, engaging in philanthropic contributions, being aware of environmental matters, and giving back to society was determined to be positively associated with improving place attractiveness and revisit intention thus implying that creating a differentiating image from other destinations is in the host places' best interest. In short, a place agent's community aligned communication efforts in tandem with his/her professional conduct embodies a transactional process which leads to recipient emotional and behavioral involvement with the place brand (Rodrigues, Borges, and Vieira, 2021).

In building upon the concept of mutual respect, Zenker and Seigis (2012) reflected upon the role of being respectful of citizen participation concerning the place planning process and discovered that the main indicator of attachment resided with the degree to which the resident perceived themselves as being an equal partner in the place planning process...meaning mutual respect is therefore an essential element to place branding. Even though not included in this study, it is quite likely that respect also plays a role in

preserving positive brand imagery with external stakeholders as well. Rodriguez, Borges, and Vieira (2021) noted that brand loyalty and brand engagement as fostered by city officials is positively accentuated when local bureaucrats link a destinations' brand commitment with CSR activities and practices designed to perpetuate place attractiveness and revisit intentions otherwise known as brand love. Continuing on the topic of being socially responsible relative to place branding, Ruffin (2008) surmised that the achievement of strategic goals within business districts are achieved by facilitating collective attainment of goals via a network of place stakeholders who openly share norms, values, and mutual place development interests. Implying, thus, of the importance of being openly transparent in their professional conduct with stakeholders.

Ethics and tourism. Sevin, E. (2011) reflected upon the evolution of what is meant by place branding and asserted that the difficulty in defining place branding is due to its roots in three distinct concepts. They proposed that place branding is a combination of internal conception (place identity), exposed identity (place brand) and audience perception (brand image). Furthermore, when communicating with stakeholders' ethical tensions can ensue when place agents decide to make validity claims of which claims may not necessarily reflect both place identity and social context. In short, declarative statements made by a place agent are expected to ethically represent place attributes. Pizzichini, Temperini, and Gregori (2020) reviewed impacts stemming from ethical attributes associated with local food souvenirs and discerned that national park attendees appeal to food souvenir purchases were associated with the ethical attributes of eco-sustainability, support of local communities, biodiversity, animal welfare, respect for human work, and freedom. Thus, showing the importance of place agents in openly and adequately communicating place branding characteristics as set within those ethical attributes. Weeden, C. (2002) conducted a study pertaining to ethical attributes associated with sustainable tourism which was premised on the mounting evidence noting that ethical concerns are part of tourists' decision-making process when selecting a destination of choice. This study comprised of United Kingdom tour operators, asserted that both tourists and tourism professionals must assume responsibility of their actions and attitudes with both parties being participants in co-creation scenarios. Weeden's overall finding was that UK tour operators did not always see significant financial gains resulting from promoting ethical tourism; however, these same place agents did express growing importance and interest in providing niche-style ethical tourism package offerings. Lastly, Inch (2011) accentuated the role of place agents in place branding and public diplomacy as reported in a special edition on place making theory and practices. The main outcome of those collected readings resulted in a call to action for place agents, agencies and impacts comprising place making to devise a process whereby place agents question and examine products and services offered for place fit and appropriateness as set within company and community values.

In closing, the aforementioned research confirms that stakeholder exchanges within the workplace are powerful, long lasting, and capable of influencing client perceptions of a company as being reputable, socially responsible, and ethical. With that concept in mind, it was worthy to evaluate the degree of influence exerted by commercial and non-commercial representatives'

leveraging of social responsibility and ethical practices as they interfaced with individuals seeking hospitality and tourism services specific to Curacao.

Materials and Methods

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of social responsibility practices and ethical practices conveyed by business representatives of commercial and non-commercial business units of which units provide services sustaining tourism within the country of Curaçao. The overarching objectives were to examine the impact of social responsibility and ethical practices upon a) the attainment of unit financial goals and b) development of strategic alliances relating to tourism perpetuation and sustainment.

As indicated above, transactions as provided by governmental and commercial entities are part of a value chain process that is intended to achieve strategic goals assigned to a business unit. Such relationship applies to an economy regardless of if it is classified as a) developed, b) economies in transition, or c) developing. Within that framework, and relative to the United Nation's financial classification (United Nations, 2022), Curaçao is classified as a developing economy. Additionally, it became clear that a void existed in studies isolating the linkage between ethical and social responsibility practices as portrayed by trade representatives of a developing island country. Curaçao, an island country located within the Caribbean, is highly dependent upon external trade transactions associated with oil refinery production, promotion of financial services, international trade, and tourism related industries (U.S. Consulate General in Curaçao, 2022a; 2022b; International Monetary Fund, 2021). Largely as a result of being geographically remote and within the aftermath of the Covid crisis, Curaçao's government put in place a national export strategy focused upon 1) real estate and tourism service promotion, 2) economic sustainability, 3) financial services, 4) port and marine services, 5) information, communication, and technological services, and 6) educational services (Tromp, 2007). Given the importance of rebounding from declining financial conditions and being geographically remote, the researchers designed a study measuring the impact of social responsibility practices and ethical work climate practices provided by the commercial and non-commercial business units of a) Curaçao's Ministry of Traffic, Transport, and Spatial Planning (TTSP), previously named the Ministry of Traffic, Transport, and Spatial Planning, b) Curaçao's Chamber of Commerce and Industry, c) Curaçao Bankers Association, and d) the Curaçao Trade and Industry Association. With that foundation in mind and within the context of proposing business strategies necessary to rebound from the previously mentioned adverse conditions, the application of socially responsible and ethical conduct practices which are known to impact attainment of strategic goals assigned to key business units became the dependent variables of the enclosed study.

Social Responsibility and Ethical Work Climates measurement instruments

In an effort to measure the respondent's perceptions of social responsibility principles/practices, ethical climate practices, and attainment of financial development goals as perceived by business clients, the model proposed by Waheed and Zhang (2020) was adopted of which the instrument consisted of thirteen social responsibility practices and principles; nine items relating to ethical

work climate practice; and two indices assigned business unit performance goals.

Table 1. Social responsibility, Ethical Climate, and Strategic Goal variables

- SR1 This unit abides by internationally recognized social responsibility standards
- SR2 This work unit has adopted industry oriented socially responsible guidelines
- SR3 This work unit complies with internal SR guidelines
- SR4 This unit recognizes anti-corruption policies
- SR5 This work unit holds official meetings with stakeholders
- SR6 This work unit applies SR principles during the procurement process
- SR7 This unit practices SR practices during the exploratory phase of the business transactions process
- SR8 SR principles are practiced with other government or commercial units
- SR9 Socially responsible practices are practiced by management, supervisors, and employees
- SR10 This work unit is involved in community engagements
- SR11 This unit is involved in community agency activities
- SR 12 This work unit offers donations to community causes

- EC1 Top managers show they care about ethics
- EC2 Top managers represent the highest ethical standards
- EC3 Top executives/managers facilitate ethical decision making
- EC4 Management disciplines unethical behavior
- EC5 Employees accept ethical rules and conduct procedures
- EC6 Rules and procedures are in place to maintain this unit's public image
- EC7 Penalties for unethical behavior are strictly reinforced
- EC8 Ethical behavior in this unit is the norm

- ED1 Attainment of annual financial goals assigned to the work unit
- ED2 Growth of high yield strategic alliances and/or partnerships

Data Collection

The researchers administered a confidential digital questionnaire to business unit managers from all four public and private commerce units. Before administering the questionnaire, these managers reviewed questionnaire content specific to the items relating to SR philosophies, SR practices, and ethical climate practices in terms of meaning and application before administering the questionnaire to tourism business clients. This process led to only minor wording modifications. As the result of receiving a listing of tourism clients from the four business unit managers, 134 digital questionnaires were submitted to 183 randomly selected tourism clients. This process yielded 52 respondents from the Chamber & Industry and Insurance sector, 30 from the banking (Bankers Association) sector, 32 from the Trade and Industry Association, and 20 from the Travel, Transportation, and Spatial Planning ministry. The resultant return rate generated a usable return rate of 73.2%.

Study Conditions

There were two conditions which led to the purpose of this study. First, social responsibility and ethical work climates can influence a client's impression as well as his/her inclination to engage in transactions with a specific provider. Second, and more importantly, no study to date had determined the effect of social responsibility and ethical climate practices upon sustaining tourism business transactions as provided by a Dutch oriented country geographically isolated in the Caribbean. As such, a particular emphasis was placed upon determining the relationship of social responsibility and ethical climate practices upon the business unit goals of a) sustaining of strategic partnerships and b) achievement of assigned financial business unit goals. For that very purpose of determining unit differences and impacts, the following six hypotheses were tested.

Study Hypotheses

The first two hypotheses (H_1 and H_2) tested for mean score differences concerning a) ethical climate practices and b) social responsibility practices as reported by perceived by business

clients. Hypothesis #3 (H_3) tested for client perceptions of mean score differences pertaining to attainment of financial goals assigned to the work unit, and hypothesis #4 (H_4) tested for mean score differences concerning high yield strategic alliance growth assigned to the respective work unit. And lastly, hypotheses (H_5 and H_6) utilized the stepwise regression procedure in an effort to test for the presence of unique combinations of EC [EC1-EC9] and SR [SR1-SR13] practices upon the variables of a) attainment of financial goals assigned to the work unit [ED1] and b) growth in externally focused high yield strategic alliance/partnership growth [ED2] for the work unit. The latter two hypotheses were expected to shed light upon managerial strategies related to maintaining and sustaining relationships as associated with the two identified dependent measurements.

- H_1 . There are no significant mean score differences of selected ethical climate indices [EC] as differentiated by business unit.
- H_2 . There are no significant mean score differences of selected social responsibility [SR] indices as differentiated by business unit.
- H_3 . There are no significant mean score differences on the emphasis placed upon attainment of annualized financial goal performance as leveraged by business unit [ED1].
- H_4 . There are no significant mean score differences on the emphasis placed upon growth via strategic high yield alliance/partnership development [ED2] as leveraged by business unit.
- H_5 . There is no statistically significant combination of EC and SR practices upon emphasis placed upon the attainment of financial goal performance as leveraged by business unit [ED1].
- H_6 . There is no statistically significant combination of EC and SR practices upon growth in strategic alliances/partnerships as leveraged by business unit [ED2].

Results and Discussions

Profile of Respondents

The individuals sampled were tourism business clients who had completed transactions as offered by the identified business units.

Of those units, (14.2%) were clients affiliated with the Chamber of Commerce, (7.2%) were from the Bankers Association, (25.2%) were from the Trade and Industry, and (32.1%) were from the Traffic Transportation and Spatial Planning office. To provide a between unit comparison, and in order to provide a baseline of agreement levels ascribed to the independent variables, the mean (\bar{x}), standard deviation (σ), and probability results are displayed in Tables 1a and 1b. In reviewing those tables, it is readily apparent that statistically significant between group differences existed on a) eight of the nine ethical climate measures, and b) seven of the eight SR measures (Tables 2 - 5).

One way Anova Findings

Findings H_1 : There are no significant mean score differences on selected ethical climate indices

(EC) as differentiated by work unit.

In deploying the Anova procedure, eight of the nine ethical climate practices showed statistically significant differences on EC1 (Mean square=3.9, $F=4.7$, $p=.001$), EC2 (Mean square=17.3, $F=20.9$, $p<.001$), EC3 (Mean square=18.5, $F=18.9$, $p<.001$), EC4 (Mean square=4.98, $F=7.6$, $p<.001$), EC5 (Mean square=3.5, $F=4.47$, $p=.002$), EC7 (Mean square=14.8, $F=20.26$, $p<.001$), EC8 (Mean square=6.6, $F=9.05$, $p<.001$), and EC9 (Mean square=3.6, $F=4.29$, $p=.002$). Hypothesis EC6 was not rejected as reflective of a Mean square of 1.28, $F=1.9$, $p=.105$. Therefore, there was general agreement across the units regarding the role of rules and procedures in maintaining a positive public image of services provided (Table 2).

The null hypotheses for eight of the nine ethical climate practices were rejected due to the presence of very strong mean score differences. Moreover, and in reflecting upon this mean and standard deviation profile it was discerned that the Traffic Transportation and Spatial Planning governmental unit commanded the lowest mean score profile and widest dispersion of scores for all nine EC dependent variables. Furthermore, and in an effort to test the strength of the association between these nine ethical climate variables as differentiated by unit affiliation the ETA procedure discerned that EC1, EC4, EC5, EC6, EC8 and EC9 were classified as small effects, while EC2, EC3, and EC7 were medium in effect thus indicating that ethical climate variables were significant in effect, albeit with differential impacts thus implying that aggregated ethical climate variable impacts were present.

Table 2. Ethical Climate Practices: \bar{x} , σ and probability profile

	Traffic Transportation and Spatial Planning	Chamber of Commerce	Bankers Association	Trade and Industry	P value	ETA
	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ		
Top managers regularly show they care about ethics (EC1)	3.51/.10	4.07/.78	3.96/.82	3.94/.89	Mean square=3.9, F=4.7, p=.001	.057
Top managers model high ethical standards (EC2)	2.96/1.00	4.07/.72	4.0/.79	3.90/.90	Mean square=17.3, F=20.9, p=<.001*	.211
Top managers guide ethical decision making (EC3)	2.97/1.12	4.11/.74	4.22/.90	3.89/.96	Mean square=18.5, F=18.9, p=<.001	.195
Management disciplines (EC4) unethical behavior	3.45/.85	4.07/.75	3.91/.84	4.0/.72	Mean square=4.98, F=7.6, p=<.001	.089
Employees accept organizational rules and procedures concerning ethical conduct (EC5)	3.57/1.0	4.04/.73	4.04/1.0	3.99/.85	Mean square=3.5, F=4.47, p=.002	.054
Organizational rule and procedures serve to maintain my unit's public image (EC6)	3.87/.88	4.16/.73	4.3/.63	4.06/.79	Mean square=1.28, F=1.9, p=.105	.024
Penalties for unethical behavior are strictly enforced (EC7)	3.11/.93	4.04/.76	3.74/.86	4.06/.78	Mean square=14.8, F=20.26, p=<.001	.206
Ethical behavior is the norm (EC8)	3.3/.93	4.02/.78	3.87/.69	3.86/.83	Mean square=6.6, F=9.05, p=<.001	.104
Ethical behavior is rewarded (EC9)	3.53/1.04	4.07/.86	4.09/.84	3.95/.84	Mean square=3.6, F=4.29, p=.002	.052

Note. Scale: 1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree

Findings H₂: There are no significant mean score differences on selected social responsibility (SR) indices as differentiated by work unit.

By means of the Anova procedure, this null hypothesis was rejected for eight of the thirteen socially responsible practices. In particular, SR1 had a Mean square of 4.4, F=5.37, p=.001; SR2 had a Mean square of 1.51, F=1.74, p=.140; SR3 had a Mean square of 8.37, F=8.5, p=<.001; SR4 had a Mean square of 2.02, F=2.42, p=<.048; SR5 had a Mean square of 14.6, F=18.65, p=<.001; SR6 had a Mean square of .147, F=.205, p=.936; SR7 had a Mean square of 1.1, F=1.44, p=.219; SR8 had a Mean square of 2.87, F=3.32, p=.011; SR9 had a Mean square of .598, F=.983, p=.417; SR10 had a Mean square of 3.89, F=6.86, p<.001; SR11 had a Mean square of 1.28, F=1.9, p=.105; SR12 had Mean square of 6.69, F=6.8, p=.001; and SR13 had a Mean square of 6.6, F=9.05, p<.001. Once again, the Traffic Transportation and Spatial Planning governmental unit displayed the lowest mean score profile and widest dispersion of scores (Table 3). Therefore, the null hypotheses for SR1, SR3, SR4, SR5, SR8, SR10, SR12, and SR13 were rejected due to the statistical presence of mean score differences.

Additionally, and in an effort to test the strength of the association between these thirteen socially responsible variables as differentiated by work unit affiliation, the ETA procedure discerned that SR1, SR2, SR4, SR6, SR7, SR8, SR9, and SR13 were classified as having a small effect, while SR3, SR10, SR11, and SR12 were medium in effect, while SR5 was large in effect thus indicating that these thirteen socially responsible

variables were recognized by the respondents as having differential effects. Overall, customers perceived that business affiliated social responsibility business practices were important to all five work units albeit to varying degrees.

Table 3. Social Responsibility Practices: \bar{x} , σ and probability profile

	Traffic Transportation and Spatial Planning	Chamber of Commerce	Bankers Association	Trade and Industry	P value	ETA
	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ		
My unit has adopted internationally CSR guidelines (SR1)	3.37/.95	3.82/.91	3.83/.98	3.96/.83	Mean square=4.4, F=5.37, p<.001	.113
My unit has adopted internal CSR guidelines (SR2)	3.77/.99	4.07/.78	3.78/1.0	3.81/.82	Mean square=1.51, F=1.74, p=.140	.052
My unit complies with internal CSR guidelines (SR3)	3.28/1.2	3.98/.81	3.87/.81	4.04/.80	Mean square=8.37, F=8.5, p<.001	.155
My unit recognizes anti-corruption policies (SR4)	3.86/.92	4.04/.79	3.96/.82	3.99/.84	Mean square=2.02, F=2.42, p=.048	.065
My unit holds regularly scheduled meetings with local authorities (SR5)	3.08/1.0	3.96/.76	3.91/.90	4.0/.82	Mean square=14.6, F=18.65, p<.001	.259
CSR during the procurement process (SR6)	4.04/.94	3.98/.81	4.13/.75	4.04/.80	Mean square=.147, F=.205, p=.936	.007
CSR during the transaction process (SR7)	3.75/.94	3.96/.70	4.17/.83	3.91/.87	Mean square=1.10, F=1.44, p=.219	.045
CSR with other government or commercial units (SR8)	3.61/1.10	4.01/.83	4.17/.77	4.0/.87	Mean square=2.87, F=3.32, p=.011	.081
Managers, supervisors, and employees practice SR (SR9)	3.9/.83	4.07/.68	3.96/.70	4.11/.71	Mean square=.598, F=.983, p=.417	.034
My unit is involved in CSR community initiatives (SR10)	3.43/.98	4.0/.76	4.17/.65	3.87/.80	Mean square=3.89, F=6.86, p<.001	.134
My unit has an established CSR policy (SR11)	3.52/.78	4.07/.75	4.13/.69	3.93/.75	Mean square=1.28, F=1.9, p=.105	.133
Donations to community agencies (SR12)	3.38/1.2	4.04/.82	4.22/.73	3.93/.92	Mean square=6.69, F=6.8, p<.001	.132
Volunteering to community initiatives (SR13)	3.73/.74	4.04/.73	4.26/.68	3.91/.76	Mean square=6.6, F=9.05, p<.001	.077

Note1. Scale: 1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree

Note2. ETA guideline (Cohen, 1992) [ES <.02 very small]; [.02<=ES<.13 Small]; [.13<=ES<.26 Medium]; [ES>=.26 Large].

Findings H₃: There are no significant mean score differences on the emphasis placed upon attainment of financial goals as leveraged by work unit [ED1].

Relative to ED1, the Anova mean score procedure as reported by customers of the assigned work units discerned that the Chamber of Commerce commanded the highest mean score rating ($\bar{x}=4.31$ $\sigma=.63$), followed by the Trade and Industry Association ($\bar{x}=3.95$ $\sigma=.87$), Bankers Association ($\bar{x}=3.83$, $\sigma=.65$), and Traffic Transportation and Spatial Planning ($\bar{x}=3.63$ $\sigma=.87$). Therefore, the ED1 null hypothesis concerning attainment of assigned financial goals was rejected with a mean square of 3.95, $F=5.5$, and p-value of $<.001$ (Table 4).

Table 4: Attainment of Economic Goals by Work Unit [ED1] \bar{x} , σ and probability profile

	Traffic Transportation and Spatial Planning	Chamber of Commerce	Bankers Association	Trade and Industry	P value	ETA
	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ		
Attainment of economic goals assigned to work unit	3.63/.87	4.31/.63	3.83/.65	3.95/.87	Mean square=3.95, $F=5.5$, $p<.001$.115

Findings H₄: There are no significant mean score differences concerning growth in strategic high yield alliance/partnership development [ED2] as leveraged by work unit.

For growth in high yield strategic alliances the Chamber of Commerce had the highest mean score ($\bar{x}=4.07$ $\sigma=.63$), followed by the Bankers Association ($\bar{x}=4.04$ $\sigma=.76$), Trade and Industry Association ($\bar{x}=3.91$ $\sigma=.67$), and lastly the Traffic Transportation and Spatial Planning ministry ($\bar{x}=3.72$ $\sigma=.72$). This statistical analysis indicates that the ED2 hypothesis could not be rejected although the probability of doing so approached the .05 level of significance (mean square=1.20, $F=2.32$, $p=.056$). The assumption, therefore, is that both private and commercial units realized the importance of maintaining external trade relations with consumer markets. Additionally, and in an effort to test the strength of the association for the two financial dependent variables as differentiated by work unit affiliation, the ETA procedure discerned that ED1 and ED2 were both classified as small effects as reported by the five reporting work units thus noting the contribution of variables although at differing levels of mean score importance.

Table 5: Growth in High Yield Strategic Alliances [ED2] \bar{x} , σ and probability profile

	Traffic Transportation and Spatial Planning	Chamber of Commerce	Bankers Association	Trade and Industry	P value	ETA
	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ	\bar{x}/σ		
Growth in high yield strategic alliances assigned by unit	3.72/.72	4.07/.63	4.04/.76	3.91/.67	Mean square=1.20, $F=2.32$, $p=.056$.063

Relative to attainment of unit financial goals (ED1 & ED2), and in keeping with the findings noted by Waheed and Zhang (2020), it was quite plausible that the attainment of established financial goals assigned to work units were multidetermined as representative of a combination of a) ethical work climate practices and b) socially responsible practices. To test the H₅ and H₆ null hypotheses, the stepwise regression procedure with the post hoc least squares difference procedure was used. The least squares test minimizes the sum of square errors which in turn increased the likelihood of predicting dependent variable effects.

Findings H₅: There is no statistically significant combination of EC and SR practices upon emphasis placed upon the attainment of financial goal performance as leveraged by work unit [ED1].

The stepwise regression procedure was used to determine the best one-level variable influence, the best two-level variable combination up to a point where multi-variable combinations no longer exerted a statistically significant effect. The entry of variables continued in an iterative fashion thus maximizing R-square in tandem with a statistically significant F-change as associated with work unit financial goal attainment [ED1].

During the initial step, EC8 (ethical behavior is the norm) exerted the best fit with an R value of .382, R-square=.146, and p value $<.001$; In step 2, EC8 combined with SR7 (This unit practices SR practices during the exploratory phase of the sales transactions process) which generated an R-value of .464, R-square=.215 and a p-value $<.001$; In step 3, EC8, SR7 and EC5 (employees accept ethical rules and conduct procedures) combined to generate an R-value of .508, R-square=.258 for a p-value $<.001$; In step 4, EC8, SR7, EC5 and EC3 (top executives facilitate ethical decision making) produced R=.532, R-square=.283 for a p-value $<.001$; in step 5, EC8, SR7, EC5, EC3 and EC9 (ethical behavior is recognized) produced R=.568, R-square=.323, for a p-value $<.001$; in step 6, EC8, SR7, EC5, EC3, and EC4 (management disciplines unethical behavior) yielded an R=.585, R-square=.342, and a p-value=.003; in step 7, EC8, SR7, EC5, EC3, EC4, and SR11 (This

unit is involved in community agency activities) generated an $R=.596$, $R\text{-square}=.356$ and a $p\text{-value}$ of $.011$; in final rotation [step 8], EC8, SR7, EC5, EC3, EC4, SR11, and SR1 combined to generate an $R=.604$, $R\text{-square}=.365$ for a $p\text{-value}$ of $.031$. As a result, the null hypothesis for H_5 was rejected. It is evident that the customers perceived ethical conduct variables along with three social responsibility variables to be vital to attainment of financial goals assigned to those work units thus implying that ED1 has multiple determinants as anchored in ethical and socially responsible variables as noted above.

Table 6. Stepwise Regression Effects: Attainment of internal financial goals assigned to this unit

Model	Change Statistics								
	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.382 ^a	.146	.143	.806	.146	53.845	1	316	<.001
2	.464 ^b	.215	.210	.774	.069	27.789	1	315	<.001
3	.508 ^c	.258	.250	.754	.043	18.068	1	314	<.001
4	.532 ^d	.283	.274	.742	.026	11.165	1	313	<.001
5	.568 ^e	.323	.312	.722	.040	18.402	1	312	<.001
6	.585 ^f	.342	.329	.713	.019	8.865	1	311	.003
7	.596 ^g	.356	.341	.707	.014	6.606	1	310	.011
8	.604 ^h	.365	.349	.703	.010	4.695	1	309	.031

Model 8 Predictors^h:

Ethical behavior in this unit is the norm (EC8); practice of SR during the exploratory phase of the sales transaction process with stakeholders (SR7); employees accept ethical rules and conduct procedures (EC5); top executives facilitate ethical decision making (EC3); management disciplines unethical behavior (EC4); ethical behavior is recognized (EC9); this unit is involved in community agency activities (SR11); this unit abides by internationally recognized social responsibility standards (SR1).

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
8 Regression	87.783	8	10.973	22.222	<.001 ⁱ
Residual	152.582	309	.494		
Total	240.365	317			

Relative to attaining financial goals assigned to the respondent’s unit, the stepwise regression procedure yielded an eight-iteration model with an initial correlation of $.382$ (model 1) with an F change of 53.845 thus resulting in a statistical probability of $<$ than $.001$ (Table 6). For the 8th iteration, the correlation was $.604$ and the adjusted $r\text{-square}$ was $.349$ and standard error of estimate was $.703$. It should be noted that indices of this magnitude are considered strong thus indicating the accuracy of the regression model (Moore et al., 2013).

In summation by variable contribution, the attainment of financial goals assigned to the respondent’s unit of employment represented a combination of a) ethical behavior in this unit is the norm, b) practice of CSR during exploratory transactions with stakeholders, c) employee acceptance of ethical guidelines, d) top executives facilitate decision making in all ethical decisions, e) management disciplines unethical behavior, f) ethical behavior is rewarded, g) this unit is involved in community agency boards, and h) this unit adopts international CSR guidelines. The Anova procedure yielded a mean square of 10.973 , $F=22.22$, at a significance level of $.001$ thus reflecting a significant influence of variables upon attainment of financial goals. Therefore, these tourism clients perceived the attainment of financial goals assigned to the respective work units to be largely a matter of establishment, deployment, oversight, and consistent application of ethical conduct throughout the trade process with a slight overlay of corporate social responsibility standards.

Findings H₆: There is no statistically significant combination of EC and SR practices upon growth in strategic alliances/partnerships as leveraged by work unit [ED2].

For the second financial growth variable via attainment of high yield alliances, the stepwise regression procedure yielded an eight-iteration model with an initial correlation of $.346$ (model 1) and an adjusted $R\text{-squared}$ value of $.117$, and a standard error of estimate of $.705$ with an F change of 43.107 thus resulting in a statistical probability of $<$ than $.001$ (Table 7). It should be noted that this variability around the estimated regression line and the accuracy of the regression model is considered strong (Moore et al., 2013); however, as other contributing factors were added into the stepwise regression model the r value increased to $.523$ in the eight iteration, the adjusted $r\text{-square}$ increased $.255$, and the

standard error of estimate leveled to .648. The r value is considered moderate, the adjusted R-square is low, while the ability for the model to predict growth in strategic high yield alliances is acceptable.

The growth in high yield strategic alliances represented a combination of a) establishment of ethical rules maintains our image, b) practice of CSR during exploratory transactions with stakeholders, c) top executives regularly show that they care about ethics, d) this unit holds regularly scheduled meetings with customers, e) this unit engages in community agency donations, f) this unit adopted international CSR guidelines, g) this unit practices CSR with customers, and h) this unit complies with internal CSR guidelines. Lastly, the associated Anova procedure yielded a sum of square of 48.956, mean square of 6.119, and F=14.575, for a significance level of < .001 thus reflecting a significant influence of the eight variables upon growth in high yield strategic alliances. It is readily apparent that customers viewed actions taken by the identified trade partner relative to attainment of high yield strategic alliances was heavily influenced by externally focused socially responsible factors versus those of internally oriented ethical practices and procedures.

Table 7. Stepwise Regression Effects: Growth in strategic ‘high yield’ alliances with external stakeholders

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.346 ^a	.120	.117	.705	.120	43.107	1	316	<.001
2	.412 ^b	.170	.165	.686	.050	19.011	1	315	<.001
3	.446 ^c	.198	.191	.675	.028	11.107	1	314	<.001
4	.473 ^d	.224	.214	.666	.025	10.264	1	313	.001
5	.490 ^e	.240	.228	.660	.016	6.500	1	312	.011
6	.499 ^f	.249	.235	.657	.010	4.002	1	311	.046
7	.514 ^g	.264	.247	.651	.014	6.053	1	310	.014
8	.523 ^h	.274	.255	.648	.010	4.327	1	309	.038

Model 8 Predictors^h:

Establishment of ethical rules maintains our image (EC); practice of CSR during exploratory transactions with stakeholders (CSR); top executives regularly show that they care about ethics (EC); my unit holds regularly scheduled meetings with local stakeholders (CSR); Community agency donations (CSR); my unit has adopted international CSR guidelines (CSR); practice of CSR with in-unit stakeholders (CSR); my unit complies with internal CSR guidelines (CSR)

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
8 Regression	48.956	8	6.119	14.575	<.001 ⁱ
Residual	129.739	309	.420		
Total	178.695	317			

Conclusions

Goede (2009) asserted that private and public service businesses were vital to Curaçao’s trade relations with Europe, North America, and Latin America of which assertion aligns nicely with Skinner ‘s assertion that a country’s strategic goal development process is strongly influenced by the presence of acceptable business practices as provided by a company’s representative (Skinner, 2019). It is worthy to note that a focus on internal financial goals as assigned to a given business unit yielded a different set of SR and EC factors versus SR and EC factors which influenced perpetuation of long-term strategic goals assigned to that same business unit. Therefore, from a management perspective, the approach taken by a company representative with a

potential business client is dependent upon the strategic goal under consideration. The management implication pertaining to social responsibility practices and ethical business practices as employed by a company representative resides in the mind of the beholder, which although not controlled but assumed in this study, is also framed within culturally acceptable mores. Thus, implying that training and tracking of internal practices is in the best interest of management given potential association with business unit organizational value systems and resultant business goal attainment.

Relative to H₅ ‘attainment of financial goals within this unit,’ four ethical climate variables interacted with four corporate social responsibility variables to generate a positive influence upon

attainment of these internal stakeholder unit's financial goals (Model 8, $R=.604$, $r\text{-square}=.365$). The implication is that these trade partners perceived a dynamic interaction of ethical climate practices along with social responsibility practices' impact upon assigned financial growth. Such a dynamic interplay between employee and management beliefs and action is typified as ethical behavior with the business unit is seen as the norm of which behavior co-aligns with internally recognized SR guidelines, relations with external stakeholders follow internally fostered SR guidelines, upper management facilitates ethical behavior, rewards appropriate behavior as well as disciplines unethical behavior, and both government and commercial business unit's outward public image requires community engagement.

Relative to H_6 'Growth in high yield strategic alliances' and given the importance of sustained trade with Caribbean countries, Latin America, North America, and Europe, the stepwise regression statistical manipulation process indicated that eight variables progressively influenced the 'growth in high yield strategic alliances.' Upon reviewing the eight predictors as detailed in Table 7 (Model 8, $R=.523$, $r\text{-square}=.274$), it became readily apparent that the role of SR principles in combination with SR practices took precedence over internal ethical climate practices. That profile is meaningful to note given that these findings versus those noted in Table 1 indicate a definite shift to the importance of SR precepts and practices as it relates to external constituencies. In particular, the establishment of ethical rules designed to maintain the business unit integrity coupled with top executives concern about ethics was of lesser yet significant importance. The remaining six SR variables entailed practicing SR practices from the inception of a business transaction, holding of meetings with external stakeholders, donating to community causes, adoption of international SR guidelines, practice of internal SR behaviors, and compliance with the established internal SR guidelines.

In closing, SR principles and practices as well as EC practices exerted a positive impact upon both short-term and long-term strategic goals, albeit at differing levels of influence for the reporting governmental and commercial units, of which findings certainly highlight the importance of management's role in devising, implementing, tracking, and providing feedback concerning adherence to established standards, policies, and procedures as important to external partners. Again, and from a managerial perspective, the training, monitoring, and reinforcement of acceptable business SR and EC practices is vital to successful goal attainment by means of combining and emphasizing certain social responsibility and ethical business practices which are of importance to external clients. Lastly, and in agreement with Waheed and Zhang (2020), SR and ethical practices are culturally (nationally) rooted and therefore differ by those factors thus stressing the importance of understanding and subsequently leveraging those specific variables when engaging in business transactions with individuals of different cultures, given potential impacts upon financial performance, sales performance, and sustaining business unit goal attainment.

Furthermore, it is also important to note that SR variables versus those of EC practices exerted the greatest amount of influence upon the perpetuation of high yield alliance/partnership relationship which is opposed to the assertion made by Waheed and Zhang (2020) whereby they asserted that EC practices were mediators of social responsibility practice which in turn influenced

upon overall sustainable business goals. This latter comment supports the contention that external forces are a) indeed culturally influenced, and b) those forces do impact how management of an island country's business unit approaches, presents services, openly communicates in ways that are meaningful to their clients, and of which actions do sustain the business representative's established strategic goals. In synopsis, the findings of this study concur with stakeholder management theory in that business representatives must be mindful of how international clients encode the social responsibility and ethical practices that we consciously or unconsciously portray while engaging in business transactions. Therefore, it is in management's best interest to ensure that their business unit representatives are positioning the proper combination of social responsibility and ethical practices during the negotiation process given how those SR and EC variables carry differing levels of importance as associated with an identified business goal.

Research Limitations

It is quite likely that the results of this study were impacted by the external environmental conditions which began in 2020 as a direct result of Covid virus outbreak, resulting in governmental shutdowns of non-essential business and curtailment of travel. Such supply chain disruption issues when placed in tandem with the highly competitive nature of trade within the Caribbean region stressed the urgency of Curaçao's governmental and commercial units to meet goals relative to finance, oil production, and tourism. However, even with those concerns stated, such conditions could quite possibly have elevated the importance of being socially responsible and acting in an ethical manner while these business representatives prospected, contracted, and serviced commercial and non-commercial transactions. It is therefore prudent to confirm the results of the current study by confirming the relationship of these corporate social responsibility and ethical climate factors under differing external conditions.

Second, the sampling of a limited number of tourism clients highlights a need to expand the range of customers surveyed in an effort to confirm the unique influence of ethical practices and socially responsibility practices upon sustained financial growth. Related to that concern, there exists a need to collect the perceptions of company representatives. The collection of such information was deemed problematic given a very small sample size, thus challenging respondent confidentiality.

Third, business unit strategic goals should be incorporated so that a more comprehensive analysis as to how SR and EC variables influence varying short term versus long term strategic goals. Other strategic goals to be considered are a) reduction in service delivery time, b) reduced operational costs, c) market share growth, d) return on investment, e) increase in overall sales volume, f) cost containment within unit, and g) net promoter scores.

Lastly, it is important to note that the respondent differences in ratings as provided by the Traffic, Transportation, and Spatial Planning Ministry versus the Chamber of Commerce, Bankers Association, and the Trade and Industry Association could be an artifact of the tangential services offered by TTSP to the tourism businesses. For instance, the tangential services offered to tourism businesses, travelers, and cruise lines concern the provision of infrastructure services such as roadways, signage, and

regulations governing transportation services versus direct drivers associated with the other business units pertaining to the creation and sustainment of tourism business engagements.

Future Research

In agreement with Goede (2009), there are additional mitigating management factors worthy of measurement inclusive of governmental practices and policies surrounding government debt levels, government budget oversight, governance practices, political unrest, elevated business transaction costs, talent dearth, supply chain costs, and elevated corporate tax rates. Therefore, studies pertaining to strategic goal attainment must be devised to measure both direct and indirect impacts of such external forces as set within an island country context.

Originality

The external forces surrounding an island economy are categorically the same as those known to influence developed economies albeit those factors for the former scale differently as a result of geographically remote conditions. Furthermore, studies focusing on how social responsibility and ethical climate practices combine to influence short term versus long terms strategic goals is relatively absent in the literature. Therefore, the enclosed study as set within Curaçao is an original attempt to statistically determine how the measured SR and EC factors combine to influence the attainment of strategic goals, both short and long term in focus.

Acknowledgement and Conflicts

None

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